

Small Language Models as Graph Classifiers: Evaluating and Improving Permutation Robustness

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Abstract. Transformer language models are increasingly used in structured domains by representing non-textual data as sequences. In the graph-as-text paradigm, graphs are serialized into textual representations and processed using standard language models for graph-level prediction. Unlike graph neural networks (GNNs), however, sequence transformers do not enforce permutation invariance: different node relabelings of the same graph yield different serialized inputs and may lead to inconsistent predictions.

We present a systematic empirical study of permutation robustness in small language models (SLMs) for graph classification, and show that multi-view consistency regularization can approximate architectural invariance. To evaluate robustness under node relabeling, we define two metrics - Flip Rate and KL-to-Mean divergence - that quantify prediction instability and confidence variation across permutations. Our analysis shows that standard fine-tuning achieves competitive accuracy but can exhibit substantial permutation sensitivity. To mitigate this limitation, we adopt a multi-view consistency objective - Permutation-Invariant Training (PIT) - that aligns predictions across randomly relabeled graph views. We additionally evaluate a minimal structural inductive bias via degree-aware token embeddings.

Our findings indicate that permutation invariance does not emerge automatically in sequence-based graph classifiers and must be explicitly encouraged through objective design. More broadly, the results show that compact language models can approximate architectural invariance through regularized training, highlighting a practical distinction between architectural and emergent symmetry in graph learning.

Keywords: Graph Classification · Small Language Models · Graph Representation Learning

1 Introduction

Graphs are a fundamental representation for structured data across domains including chemistry, biology, and social networks. Graph classification - the task of

assigning a label to an entire graph - is traditionally addressed using graph neural networks (GNNs), which explicitly encode permutation-invariant inductive biases through message passing and symmetric aggregation. These architectural constraints guarantee that predictions remain unchanged under node relabeling, a defining structural property of graphs.

Recently, transformer-based language models have demonstrated surprising versatility beyond natural language processing. A growing line of work applies language models to structured inputs by serializing non-textual data into textual form. In the graph domain, this graph-as-text paradigm represents nodes and edges as sequences of tokens and applies standard language-model fine-tuning procedures for graph-level prediction. This raises a fundamental question: to what extent can small language models act as graph classifiers when graphs are represented as text, and how robust are such models to graph symmetries?

In this work, we show that small language models (SLMs) can serve as competitive graph classifiers without graph-specific architectural modifications. We cast graph classification as next-token prediction: after a serialized graph representation, the model predicts a single class token. Using parameter-efficient fine-tuning (LoRA) and stratified cross-validation on benchmark datasets, we demonstrate that compact transformer models achieve performance comparable to widely used GNN baselines across multiple graph classification tasks.

However, unlike GNNs, sequence transformers do not inherently enforce permutation invariance. Under serialization, node ordering becomes part of the input, so isomorphic graphs with different labelings produce different sequences. As a result, predictions may vary under relabeling even when the underlying graph structure is unchanged. We therefore systematically investigate permutation robustness in SLM-based graph classifiers. Beyond predictive accuracy, we introduce an explicit evaluation protocol. For each graph, we generate multiple random node relabelings and measure: (i) *Flip Rate*, the fraction of relabelings that change the predicted class; and (ii) *KL-to-Mean divergence*, which quantifies instability of the predictive distribution across relabelings. These metrics quantify decision and confidence instability under permutation.

To improve robustness, we investigate two complementary mechanisms. First, we adopt Permutation-Invariant Training (PIT), a multi-view consistency objective that regularizes predictions across relabeled graph views. Second, we incorporate a minimal structural inductive bias through degree-aware token embeddings, which inject permutation-invariant structural information into the model without modifying the transformer architecture.

Our empirical results reveal a consistent pattern. Small language models can achieve competitive graph classification performance under textual serialization, but permutation robustness does not emerge automatically from fine-tuning. Consistency-based regularization substantially reduces permutation sensitivity and often improves accuracy; on more complex datasets, combining structural bias with PIT further strengthens robustness, whereas structural bias alone is insufficient. These findings highlight a gap between predictive accuracy and permutation robustness in graph-as-text models and demonstrate that invariance

in sequence-based classifiers must be explicitly induced rather than assumed.

Contributions The contributions of this work are as follows:

- To our knowledge, we present the first systematic study of small language models (SLMs) as graph classifiers under the graph-as-text paradigm, evaluating both predictive performance and permutation robustness.
- We introduce two quantitative robustness metrics, *Flip Rate* and *KL-to-Mean divergence*, to measure prediction and confidence instability under node relabeling.
- We demonstrate that Permutation-Invariant Training (PIT), a multi-view consistency objective over relabeled graph views, substantially improves permutation robustness and often enhances classification accuracy across multiple backbones and benchmark datasets.

2 Related Work

Language models for graph classification. Rapid progress in language models has expanded their application to structured data. In the graph-as-text paradigm, graphs are serialized into textual sequences and processed by pretrained language models. Prior work such as GraphGPT [1], GraphLLM [2], and related approaches [3, 4] explores reasoning and prediction over serialized graphs. However, these studies primarily focus on large-scale LLMs and reasoning-oriented benchmarks rather than standard graph classification under controlled cross-validation protocols. The role of compact small language models (SLMs) as competitive graph classifiers has not been systematically evaluated.

Permutation invariance in graph learning. Permutation invariance is fundamental to graph representation learning: graph-level predictions must remain unchanged under node relabeling. Message-passing GNNs such as GCN [5], GraphSAGE [6], GAT [7], and GIN [8] guarantee invariance through symmetric aggregation. Transformer-based graph models such as Graphormer [10], SAN [11], and GPS [12] preserve invariance through structure-aware encodings. In contrast, serialized graphs processed by generic sequence models lack architectural symmetry guarantees. We therefore treat permutation robustness as an explicit evaluation criterion and design training mechanisms to approximate invariance in SLM-based graph classification.

Consistency and invariance learning. Our Permutation-Invariant Training objective relates to consistency regularization and multi-view learning, including Temporal Ensembling [13], Mean Teacher [14], and augmentation-based methods [15]. In graph learning, augmentations such as GraphCL [16] improve generalization but alter structure. Node relabeling, by contrast, preserves graph structure exactly and represents a symmetry transformation. We explicitly measure permutation sensitivity and enforce multi-view consistency to encourage symmetry without modifying the transformer architecture.

3 Method

3.1 Problem Formulation

Let $G = (V, E, X)$ denote a graph with node set V , edge set E , and node features X . In graph classification, the objective is to learn a function $f(G)$ that predicts a graph-level label y . In this study, we consider binary graph classification tasks, where $y \in \{0, 1\}$ denotes one of two graph-level classes.

A fundamental property of graph learning is permutation invariance: for any node relabeling (permutation) π ,

$$f(G) = f(\pi(G)).$$

In a graph-as-text setting, however, this invariance is not guaranteed, since different node orderings produce different serialized sequences.

3.2 Graph-to-Text Serialization

Each graph is converted into an adjacency-list textual representation:

```
GRAPH n=|V| m=|E|
NODE u <node_repr(u)> : v1 v2 ... vk
...
```

Node representations include either: (i) discrete labels encoded as `lab=<id>`, or (ii) truncated continuous feature vectors formatted as `feat=[...]`.

This format exposes both topology and node attributes while remaining compatible with standard transformer language models.

3.3 Classification via Next-Token Prediction

Graph classification is cast as next-token prediction. Given a serialized graph $S(G)$, we append the prompt suffix:

Class:

The model predicts a single-token label (e.g., “0” or “1”).

Let $h(G)$ denote the hidden state at the final token position. Class probabilities are computed as:

$$p(y | G) = \text{softmax}(Wh(G)),$$

where W selects logits corresponding to label tokens.

Training minimizes class-weighted cross-entropy:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{sup}} = - \sum_i w_{y_i} \log p(y_i | G_i),$$

where weights w_{y_i} compensate for class imbalance within each fold.

3.4 Permutation-Invariant Training (PIT)

To encourage robustness under node relabeling, we apply a multi-view consistency objective - Permutation-Invariant Training (PIT) - to the graph-as-text setting. This objective can be interpreted as approximating risk minimization over permutation orbits by aligning predictive distributions across relabeled views.

For each graph, we generate K random relabeled views:

$$\{G^{(1)}, \dots, G^{(K)}\}.$$

In addition to supervised loss, we enforce prediction consistency across views using KL-to-Mean divergence to the mean distribution:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{cons}} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \text{KL} \left(p(y | G^{(k)}) \parallel \bar{p}(y) \right),$$

where $\bar{p}(y)$ is the average prediction across views.

The total training objective becomes:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{sup}} + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{\text{cons}},$$

with λ controlling consistency strength.

3.5 Structural Bias: Degree-Aware Token Embedding

We further investigate minimal structural inductive bias through degree-aware token embeddings.

For each node u , its degree $\text{deg}(u)$ is bucketed into discrete intervals. All tokens corresponding to the line

NODE u . . .

receive an additional learned embedding $e_{\text{deg}(u)}$ added to the token embedding:

$$\tilde{x}_t = x_t + e_{\text{deg}(u)}.$$

This modification preserves the transformer architecture while injecting structural information that is invariant to node permutations.

3.6 Permutation Robustness Metrics

To quantify permutation sensitivity, we evaluate each trained model under multiple random node relabelings.

For each graph G , we generate R relabeled variants and compute:

Flip Rate. Let $\{\hat{y}^{(1)}, \dots, \hat{y}^{(R)}\}$ denote the predicted class labels obtained from R independently relabeled versions of a graph G . Let

$$\hat{y}^* = \text{mode} \left(\hat{y}^{(1)}, \dots, \hat{y}^{(R)} \right)$$

denote the modal (most frequent) predicted label across relabelings. In the rare case of ties, one of the tied labels is selected arbitrarily.

The Flip Rate of G is defined as

$$\text{FlipRate}(G) = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R \mathbf{1} \left[\hat{y}^{(r)} \neq \hat{y}^* \right],$$

where $\mathbf{1}[\cdot]$ denotes the indicator function.

Flip Rate measures the fraction of node relabelings that produce a prediction different from the modal class, thereby quantifying decision instability under permutation.

KL-to-Mean divergence. Confidence instability is measured as:

$$\text{KL-to-Mean}(G) = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R \text{KL} \left(p^{(r)}(y) \parallel \bar{p}(y) \right),$$

where $\bar{p}(y)$ is the mean predicted distribution.

4 Experiments and Results

4.1 Datasets

We evaluate on five TU benchmark datasets [19]: PROTEINS, MUTAG, BZR, PTC_MR, and IMDB-BINARY. These datasets span molecular, biological, and social-network graphs with varying sizes and feature availability, enabling evaluation across different levels of structural complexity.

4.2 Models

All experiments employ pretrained small instruction-tuned language models as backbone architectures, specifically **Llama-3.2-1B-Instruct** [20], **Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct** [21], and **SmolLM2-1.7B-Instruct** [22]. These models span the 1–2B parameter range and represent compact, publicly available instruction-tuned transformers. We select instruction-tuned variants because graph classification is formulated as prompt completion (next-token prediction of a class label), and instruction tuning improves stability and consistency in conditional generation settings.

We fine-tune the selected models for graph classification using Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) [17]. LoRA modules are applied to attention and MLP projection layers (rank $r = 16$, scaling $\alpha = 32$, dropout 0.05). Quantized 4-bit loading (QLoRA-style [18]) is used to reduce memory footprint.

4.3 Experimental Protocol

All experiments use stratified K -fold cross-validation (default $K = 10$). Within each fold, a validation subset is extracted from the training partition for model selection. We report mean \pm standard deviation across folds.

We evaluate four configurations:

1. **Baseline**: single-view fine-tuning without consistency regularization.
2. **PIT**: multi-view consistency training with $\lambda > 0$ (default $\lambda = 10$).
3. **Degree Bias**: degree-aware token embedding without consistency regularization.
4. **Degree Bias + PIT**: combination of structural bias and multi-view consistency.

Training hyperparameters are kept fixed across configurations for fairness.

4.4 GNN Baselines

To provide permutation-invariant references, we evaluate four standard message-passing GNNs: GCN, GraphSAGE, GIN, and GAT. For fair comparison, we implement all GNN baselines under a unified architectural and training configuration. All models use three message-passing layers (hidden size 128), ReLU activations, 0.5 dropout, and a two-layer MLP classifier. Graph representations are obtained via global mean pooling (GCN, GraphSAGE, GAT) or global sum pooling (GIN). Training follows the same stratified 10-fold cross-validation protocol as the language-model experiments.

4.5 Results

Table 1 reports 10-fold cross-validation accuracy across datasets for all SLM configurations and GNN baselines. Compact instruction-tuned SLMs achieve competitive performance relative to permutation-invariant GNNs, and in several cases match or surpass them in accuracy. PIT consistently improves or maintains accuracy. While degree-aware embeddings alone produce mixed results, combining them with PIT often strengthens performance.

Permutation robustness metrics are summarized in Table 2. Baseline SLM models exhibit non-trivial Flip Rates and KL-to-Mean divergence under random node relabeling, indicating sensitivity to serialization order. In several settings, PIT reduces Flip Rate from above 0.1 to below 0.02, indicating near-invariant behavior under random relabeling. Degree bias provides limited and inconsistent robustness improvements.

The effect of consistency strength λ and number of relabeled views V is shown in Table 3. Increasing V and λ generally improves robustness, with diminishing returns at higher values. Moderate consistency strength frequently improves both robustness and accuracy.

Figure 1 visualizes the relationship between accuracy and permutation stability. Across models and datasets, PIT shifts performance toward higher stability while preserving or improving predictive accuracy.

Table 1. 10-fold cross-validation accuracy (mean \pm std) across datasets for GNN baselines and SLMs. Bold indicates the best overall result per dataset; underlined values denote the best result within each block (GNN baselines or SLMs).

Model	PROTEINS	MUTAG	BZR	PTC_MR	IMDB-BINARY
GNN Baselines					
GCN	0.7071 \pm 0.0466	0.6865 \pm 0.0961	<u>0.8099 \pm 0.0419</u>	0.5608 \pm 0.0517	0.6950 \pm 0.0453
GIN	<u>0.7134 \pm 0.0372</u>	<u>0.7822 \pm 0.0795</u>	0.7951 \pm 0.0194	0.5810 \pm 0.0508	0.7134 \pm 0.0372
SAGE	0.6901 \pm 0.0767	0.7018 \pm 0.0731	0.7924 \pm 0.0416	0.5603 \pm 0.0809	0.6660 \pm 0.0566
GAT	0.7035 \pm 0.0579	0.6754 \pm 0.0840	0.7927 \pm 0.0149	<u>0.5903 \pm 0.0495</u>	0.6400 \pm 0.0435
Small Language Models (Graph-as-Text)					
<i>Llama-3.2-1B-Instruct</i>					
Baseline	0.6909 \pm 0.0414	0.8082 \pm 0.0366	0.7401 \pm 0.0876	0.5292 \pm 0.0508	0.6570 \pm 0.0537
PIT	0.7284 \pm 0.0376	0.8235 \pm 0.0839	0.8100 \pm 0.0412	<u>0.5774 \pm 0.0798</u>	0.6780 \pm 0.0368
Degree	0.6963 \pm 0.0345	0.7982 \pm 0.0932	0.7135 \pm 0.1001	0.5229 \pm 0.0719	0.6240 \pm 0.0651
Degree + PIT	<u>0.7375 \pm 0.0361</u>	<u>0.8315 \pm 0.0569</u>	<u>0.8144 \pm 0.0270</u>	0.5765 \pm 0.0627	0.6987 \pm 0.0488
<i>Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct</i>					
Baseline	0.6775 \pm 0.0731	0.8085 \pm 0.0715	0.7684 \pm 0.1028	0.5469 \pm 0.0744	0.6320 \pm 0.0354
PIT	0.7332 \pm 0.0385	<u>0.8632 \pm 0.0721</u>	0.8052 \pm 0.0363	0.5588 \pm 0.0409	0.6818 \pm 0.0293
Degree	0.7017 \pm 0.0534	0.7982 \pm 0.0769	0.6498 \pm 0.1490	0.5231 \pm 0.0673	0.6330 \pm 0.0494
Degree + PIT	<u>0.7509 \pm 0.0320</u>	0.8148 \pm 0.1228	0.8032 \pm 0.0401	<u>0.5663 \pm 0.0208</u>	0.6935 \pm 0.0407
<i>SmolLM2-1.7B-Instruct</i>					
Baseline	0.7162 \pm 0.0428	0.8354 \pm 0.0719	0.6912 \pm 0.1446	0.5520 \pm 0.0884	0.6210 \pm 0.0301
PIT	0.7294 \pm 0.0366	0.8567 \pm 0.0681	0.8032 \pm 0.0309	0.5661 \pm 0.1028	<u>0.6983 \pm 0.0242</u>
Degree	0.7179 \pm 0.0305	0.8357 \pm 0.0538	0.7305 \pm 0.0993	0.5463 \pm 0.0659	0.6310 \pm 0.0481
Degree + PIT	0.7514 \pm 0.0327	0.8662 \pm 0.0674	<u>0.8041 \pm 0.0408</u>	0.5973 \pm 0.0881	0.6905 \pm 0.0365

4.6 Analysis

We analyze the findings along three dimensions: (i) predictive competitiveness relative to invariant GNNs, (ii) the structural origin of permutation sensitivity, and (iii) the mechanisms through which multi-view consistency induces emergent invariance.

Predictive capacity without architectural bias. SLMs approximate the predictive capacity of invariant GNNs despite lacking symmetric aggregation. This suggests that next-token prediction over adjacency-list representations is sufficiently expressive to capture discriminative structural patterns. The consistent accuracy gains under PIT further indicate that enforcing agreement across permutations can regularize representations and improve generalization in the absence of architectural inductive bias.

Structural origin of permutation sensitivity. Baseline instability reveals a structural asymmetry introduced by linearization. Token position encodes incidental ordering information, allowing the model to exploit serialization-specific correlations rather than graph structure. Thus, correctness under a fixed ordering does not imply symmetry-consistent decision boundaries. Dataset-dependent variation in instability further suggests that structural heterogeneity amplifies reliance on order-specific signals. More complex datasets provide greater opportunity for spurious positional correlations, while simpler datasets reduce - but do not eliminate - such effects.

Table 2. Permutation robustness metrics (Flip Rate ↓, KL-to-Mean ↓) across datasets for SLMs under different training configurations.

Method	PROTEINS		MUTAG		BZR		PTC_MR		IMDB-BINARY	
	Flip	KL	Flip	KL	Flip	KL	Flip	KL	Flip	KL
<i>Llama-3.2-1B-Instruct</i>										
Baseline	0.1163	0.1380	0.0513	0.0722	0.0781	0.1320	0.2708	0.3385	0.1218	0.1076
PIT	0.0151	0.0030	0.0058	0.0020	0.0075	0.0018	0.0378	0.0024	0.0117	0.0005
Degree	0.1089	0.1084	0.1202	0.1427	0.1263	0.1773	0.2500	0.2687	0.1457	0.0760
Degree + PIT	0.0177	0.0044	0.0367	0.0097	0.0252	0.0143	0.1062	0.0110	0.0361	0.0042
<i>Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct</i>										
Baseline	0.0805	0.0818	0.0313	0.0361	0.0872	0.1037	0.1388	0.1420	0.1479	0.1358
PIT	0.0190	0.0055	0.0087	0.0003	0.0082	0.0017	0.0388	0.0015	0.0299	0.0015
Degree	0.0897	0.0807	0.0983	0.1374	0.1430	0.1464	0.1851	0.1605	0.1283	0.0927
Degree + PIT	0.0140	0.0043	0.0168	0.0043	0.0239	0.0053	0.0588	0.0062	0.0273	0.0014
<i>SmolLM2-1.7B-Instruct</i>										
Baseline	0.0950	0.1333	0.0671	0.0732	0.1462	0.1894	0.1786	0.1112	0.2041	0.1987
PIT	0.0189	0.0038	0.0121	0.0012	0.0061	0.0008	0.0224	0.0009	0.0277	0.0023
Degree	0.0961	0.1330	0.0650	0.0470	0.1063	0.1393	0.1332	0.0820	0.1733	0.1273
Degree + PIT	0.0145	0.0041	0.0077	0.0017	0.0044	0.0008	0.0377	0.0012	0.0254	0.0021

Consistency as representation-level symmetry induction. Multi-view consistency reshapes the decision function rather than merely averaging predictions. By minimizing divergence across relabeled views, PIT encourages the model to encode features that remain stable under permutation. This induces invariance at the representation level without modifying the underlying transformer architecture. The observed joint improvement in stability and accuracy suggests that order-dependent variability acts as a source of training noise, and suppressing it yields more robust decision boundaries.

Limits of structural bias. Degree-aware embeddings alone do not eliminate permutation sensitivity. Although degree is permutation-invariant, augmenting token representations with invariant features does not prevent downstream layers from exploiting order-dependent signals elsewhere in the sequence. This highlights the distinction between injecting invariant features and enforcing invariant functions. Structural bias becomes effective primarily when combined with objective-level consistency constraints.

Architectural versus emergent invariance. Taken together, the findings reveal a fundamental distinction between architectural and emergent symmetry. GNNs guarantee permutation invariance through symmetric aggregation. In contrast, sequence models initially learn order-dependent functions but can approximate invariance through regularized training. While the learned symmetry is empirical rather than guaranteed over the full permutation group, the substantial reduction in instability demonstrates that objective-level regularization can partially substitute for architectural constraints in sufficiently expressive models.

Table 3. Effect of Permutation-Invariant Training (PIT) across consistency strength λ and number of relabeled views V . Results are mean \pm std over 10-fold cross-validation. Baseline (no PIT) performance is reported in parentheses next to each model name. Best values per model are bolded.

V	$\lambda = 1$			$\lambda = 10$		
	Acc \uparrow	Flip \downarrow	KL \downarrow	Acc \uparrow	Flip \downarrow	KL \downarrow
Llama-3.2-1B-Instruct (BZR) (Baseline: 0.7401 \pm 0.0876 0.0781 \pm 0.0561 0.1320 \pm 0.0780)						
2	0.7652 \pm 0.0547	0.0883 \pm 0.0888	0.1080 \pm 0.0913	0.7962 \pm 0.0439	0.0374 \pm 0.0315	0.0296 \pm 0.0373
4	0.7766 \pm 0.0430	0.0669 \pm 0.0408	0.0617 \pm 0.0400	0.8100 \pm 0.0412	0.0075 \pm 0.0060	0.0018 \pm 0.0013
8	0.7975 \pm 0.0368	0.0382 \pm 0.0363	0.0232 \pm 0.0203	0.8108 \pm 0.0344	0.0013 \pm 0.0026	0.0003 \pm 0.0002
Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct (MUTAG) (Baseline: 0.8085 \pm 0.0715 0.0313 \pm 0.0270 0.0361 \pm 0.0275)						
2	0.8463 \pm 0.0709	0.0452 \pm 0.0230	0.0482 \pm 0.0264	0.8566 \pm 0.0695	0.0146 \pm 0.0211	0.0025 \pm 0.0016
4	0.8407 \pm 0.0800	0.0227 \pm 0.0298	0.0094 \pm 0.0117	0.8632 \pm 0.0721	0.0087 \pm 0.0159	0.0003 \pm 0.0002
8	0.8449 \pm 0.0322	0.0196 \pm 0.0314	0.0032 \pm 0.0030	0.8678 \pm 0.0497	0.0059 \pm 0.0080	0.0001 \pm 0.0001

Fig. 1. Accuracy versus permutation stability ($1 - \text{Flip Rate}$) for Baseline and PIT across datasets. Hollow markers denote standard fine-tuning (Baseline), while filled markers denote Permutation-Invariant Training (PIT). Line segments connect paired results on the same dataset, illustrating the effect of PIT. Higher values on both axes indicate better performance.

5 Limitations

Despite the empirical findings presented in this work, several limitations should be acknowledged.

First, Permutation-Invariant Training (PIT) introduces additional computational overhead due to multi-view training. The number of relabeled views influences both training cost and robustness, and optimal settings may depend on dataset structure. The scalability of this approach to substantially larger graphs or longer serialized sequences remains uncertain.

Second, robustness is evaluated under random node relabelings within a fixed serialization scheme. While this isolates sensitivity to identifier ordering, it does not assess robustness under alternative linearization strategies or systematically adversarial permutations.

Third, our study focuses on compact instruction-tuned models in the 1-2B parameter range. The behavior of larger language models, different pretraining regimes, or multi-class settings may differ and warrants further investigation.

6 Conclusion

We investigated small language models (SLMs) as graph classifiers in the graph-as-text paradigm, evaluating both predictive accuracy and permutation robustness under node relabeling. Compact instruction-tuned transformers achieve competitive graph classification performance without graph-specific architectural modifications; however, competitive accuracy does not imply structural consistency, as standard fine-tuning yields predictions that vary across isomorphic graph serializations.

To address this gap, we introduced explicit permutation robustness metrics and applied Permutation-Invariant Training (PIT), a multi-view consistency objective aligning predictions across relabeled graph views. PIT substantially reduces permutation sensitivity while often improving accuracy. In contrast, minimal structural bias through degree-aware embeddings alone is insufficient, indicating that invariance must be enforced at the objective level rather than assumed to emerge from enriched token representations.

Overall, our findings establish a practical distinction between architectural and emergent symmetry in graph learning: while GNNs guarantee invariance by construction, sequence-based models can approximate it through regularized training. More broadly, the results demonstrate that compact language models are viable structured predictors beyond natural language when domain-specific symmetries are explicitly evaluated and encouraged. Future work may explore scalability, alternative serialization strategies, and theoretical limits of learned invariance.

References

1. Tang, J., Yang, Y., Wei, W., Shi, L., Su, L., Cheng, S., Yin, D., Huang, C.: GraphGPT: Graph instruction tuning for large language models. arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.13023 (2023)
2. Chai, Z., Zhang, T., Wu, L., Han, K., Hu, X., Huang, X., Yang, Y.: GraphLLM: Boosting graph reasoning ability of large language models. arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.05845 (2023)
3. Li, Y., Li, Z., Wang, P., Li, J., Sun, X., Cheng, H., Yu, J.X.: A survey of graph meets large language model: Progress and future directions. arXiv preprint arXiv:2311.12399 (2023)
4. Yao, L., Peng, J., Mao, C., Luo, Y.: Exploring large language models for knowledge graph completion. arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.13916 (2023)
5. Kipf, T.N., Welling, M.: Semi-supervised classification with graph convolutional networks. In: International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR) (2017)
6. Hamilton, W., Ying, R., Leskovec, J.: Inductive representation learning on large graphs. In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), vol. 30 (2017)

7. Veličković, P., Cucurull, G., Casanova, A., Romero, A., Liò, P., Bengio, Y.: Graph attention networks. In: International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR) (2018)
8. Xu, K., Hu, W., Leskovec, J., Jegelka, S.: How powerful are graph neural networks? arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.00826 (2018)
9. Morris, C., Ritzert, M., Fey, M., Hamilton, W.L., Lenssen, J.E., Rattan, G., Grohe, M.: Weisfeiler and Leman go neural: Higher-order graph neural networks. arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.02244 (2018)
10. Ying, C., Cai, T., Luo, S., Zheng, S., Ke, G., He, D., Shen, Y., Liu, T.-Y.: Do transformers really perform badly for graph representation? In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), vol. 34 (2021)
11. Kreuzer, D., Beaini, D., Hamilton, W.L., Létourneau, V., Tossou, P.: Rethinking graph transformers with spectral attention. In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), vol. 34 (2021)
12. Rampášek, L., Galkin, M., Dwivedi, V.P., Luu, A.T., Wolf, G., Beaini, D.: Recipe for a general, powerful, scalable graph transformer. In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), vol. 35 (2022)
13. Laine, S., Aila, T.: Temporal ensembling for semi-supervised learning. In: International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR) (2017)
14. Tarvainen, A., Valpola, H.: Mean teachers are better role models: Weight-averaged consistency targets improve semi-supervised deep learning results. In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), vol. 30 (2017)
15. Sohn, K., Berthelot, D., Li, C.-L., Zhang, Z., Carlini, N., Cubuk, E.D., Kurakin, A., Zhang, H., Raffel, C.: FixMatch: Simplifying semi-supervised learning with consistency and confidence. In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), vol. 33 (2020)
16. You, Y., Chen, T., Sui, Y., Chen, T., Wang, Z., Shen, Y.: Graph contrastive learning with augmentations. In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), vol. 33 (2020)
17. Hu, E.J., Shen, Y., Wallis, P., Allen-Zhu, Z., Li, Y., Wang, S., Wang, L., Chen, W.: LoRA: Low-rank adaptation of large language models. arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.09685 (2021)
18. Dettmers, T., Pagnoni, A., Holtzman, A., Zettlemoyer, L.: QLoRA: Efficient fine-tuning of quantized LLMs. In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), vol. 36 (2023)
19. Morris, C., Kriege, N.M., Bause, F., Kersting, K., Mutzel, P., Neumann, M.: TU-Dataset: A collection of benchmark datasets for learning with graphs. In: ICML Workshop on Graph Representation Learning and Beyond (2020)
20. Llama Team: The Llama 3 Herd of Models. arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.21783 (2024)
21. Qwen Team: Qwen2.5 Technical Report. arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.15115 (2024)
22. Ben Allal, L., Lozhkov, A., Bakouch, E., Martín Blázquez, G., Penedo, G., Tunstall, L., Marafioti, A., Kydlíček, H., Piqueres Lajarín, A., Srivastav, V., Lochner, J., Fahlgrén, C., Nguyen, X.-S., Fourrier, C., Burtenshaw, B., Larcher, H., Zhao, H., Zakka, C., Morlon, M., Raffel, C., von Werra, L., Wolf, T.: SmolLM2: When smol goes big – data-centric training of a small language model. arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.02737 (2025)